

E-Commerce Success Analysis in India A Comprehensive Research

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Abstract This research paper aims to analyze the success factor and challenger of e-commerce in Indian Market. By examining key trends, consumer behavior, regulatory landscape and technological advancement, recognize insights in to the factor contributing to success of e-commerce in India and how e-commerce market making a reach towards Indian citizens from big cities to villages. Maximum facilities are available to consumer by a single click. Wide range of products are available with return policy. Consumers are choosing their desired product with different offers. E-commerce provides any time purchasing facility to consumer. The National E-commerce policy aim to create a framework for achieving holistic growth of E-commerce sector along with existing policies of Make in India and Digital India. Inclusive growth of the sector will be important catalyst for achieving economic growth and other public policy objectives.

Keywords GeM- Government-e-Market Place, GVM - Gross Merchandise Value, CAGR - Compound Annual Growth Rate, PE/VC - Private Equity / Venture Capital, 3PL- Third Party Logistics.

Introduction

In recent years, India has witnessed an unprecedented surge in e-commerce, catalyzed by factor such as rapid digitalization, increasing internet penetration and a burgeoning middle class eager to embrace online shopping. This seismic shift has not only transformed the way Indians shop but has also opened up vast opportunities for businesses, both large and small, to thrive in this dynamic marketplace. From the convenience of mobile payments to the vast array to choices available at the click of a button, e-commerce has become synonymous with accessibility and affordability for millions across the nation. As India continues its journey towards becoming a digital powerhouse, the trajectory of e-commerce growth, shows no signs of slowing down, promising a future where the virtual market place is integral to Indian life or its bustling market.

In addition to the convenience and accessibility that e-commerce brings to consumers, its impact on the Indian economy can not be overstated. The rapid growth of e-commerce has led to job creation across various sectors from logistics and delivery services to digital marketing and customer support. Small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) have found a level playing field in the digital realm, enabling them to reach a wider audience and compete with established player like never before. As we look ahead e-commerce growth in India is poised to redefine the way business operate and consumer interact with brands.

Objective of study

1. Determine the critical factors contributing to the success of e-commerce business in India.
2. Analyze the overall e-commerce landscape in India, including market size, growth rate and competitive dynamics.
3. Investigating the preferences, purchasing patterns of Indian Consumers in e-commerce space.

Review of Literature

i. Indian Trent Book 2021 - The Indian internet and e-commerce sector has mushroomed to become one of the fastest growing sector of the country, even in the pandemic hit economy. Since & most of the e-commerce companies have an a variety business model

with high cash burn rates, they witnessed significant reduction in investment interest during 2020. None the less most of the leading e-commerce companies have bounced back smartly with improved business metrics and sector is expected to remain recipients of PE/VC investment in the coming years.

ii. E-Commerce Conference Nov. 17, 2023 FICCI, New Delhi - The past two decades has been seen a remarkable transformation in global trading and commerce and India has been no exception. E-commerce and e-commerce platforms have not only permitted the existing Indian market thereby changing traditional forms of business but have also given impetus to the startup eco system in India.

iii. India Brand Equity Foundation Report Dec. 2023 - India's E-commerce sector has transformed the way business is done in India and has opened various segment of commerce ranging from business to business (B2B), Direct To Consumer (D2C), Consumer to Consumer (C2C) and consumer to business (C2B). Major segments such as D2C and B2B have experienced immense growth in recent years.

iv. India Venture Capital Report 2022 - With in Consumer tech, several alternative formats of commerce saw significant funding, such as vedio commerce, direct to consumer (D2C), brand aggregator models and short-form videos. Online business to business (B2B) market places saw traction as four new unicorns were created, large opportunity sign driven by the pandemic-led-inflection in digital adoption with in B2C supply chain.

v. Unlocking the potential of MSMEs in e-commerce, March 2022 NASSCOM Report -

The Indian e-commerce sector is a powerful ally to the government and plays a key role in the overall growth of the Indian economy. Over the past few years, India has seen a surge in small enterprises and homemakers scaling their business. While it is true that in the future these small retail players will continue to be the backbone of the Indian retail Industry, the new way forward for them would be to transform from offline mode to an "Offline + Online" mode of business.

Methodology

This research paper is based on secondary source. The data is collected from various reports newspapers, articles and books which were in public domain. Internet played a important role in collecting the data.

Analysis

Government Policies on e-commerce - A draft of National e-commerce policy has been prepared and placed in public domain. This policy addresses six broad areas of e-commerce ecosystem viz. data, infrastructure, development, e-commerce marketplaces, regulatory issues, stimulating domestic digital economy and export promotion through e-commerce. The Policy takes in to account interests of all stakeholders like investors, manufacturers, MSMEs, traders, retailers, startups and consumers. The FDI Policy on e-commerce, first pronounced through Press Note 2 of 2000 permitted 100% FDI in B2B e-commerce activity. B2C e-commerce that is multi-brand retail through inventory based model, has all along remained prohibited for FDI. Through the press note 2 (2018) issued on 26 December, 2018 Government has only reiterated the policy provision to ensure better implementation of the policy in letter and spirit, without making any change in the underlying principals.

The e-commerce sector has recorded a cumulative total of US\$ 28.5 billion in PE/VC investment across 942 dealer increasing from US\$ 311 million in 2011 to a high US\$ 5.1 billion 2018, a 16-fold increase over eight years. However in 2020, e-commerce sector recorded US\$ 2.8 billion in investment, a 53% decline compared to 2019, largely on account of the pandemic which saw PE/VC fund pullback on investment outlays in to business with significant cash burn rates in the absence of sales/revenue visibility. Since most of the e-commerce companies have an evolving business model with high cash burn rates.

The Online retail market in India is estimated to be 25% of the total organized retail market and is expected to reach 37% by 2030. By 2034, it is predicted to surpass the United States to become the second largest e-commerce market globally, after China.

In order to tap into this large market, the e-commerce industry has also seen an increase in innovation across platforms and ancillary segments such as logistics. E-commerce segment that are expected to see some strong action in the coming years include -

i. Online Grocery - Entry of Reliance Group and Tata Group will spur competition and even consolidation.

ii. E- Pharmacy - Consolidation underway in the sector and strong tailwinds from rapid digital adoption post Covid-19.

iii. Social Commerce - Increased Investment by venture funds and focus of companies like Facebook, Google, SnapChat and others.

iv. Super Apps - Mobile application that offer various services within a single app are expected to pick up traction. Whatsapp is already making strides in this direction with introduction of payments and shopping features.

The growth e-commerce will also drive allied industries such as logistics, supply chain, agri-tech and omnichannel sales solutions, which have already received higher investment in 2020.

Source: EY analysis of VCCEdge data

E-commerce, fintech, AI and SaaS are top four core sector of world's unicorns, making up 45.9% of the sectoral universe of these unicorns. In India one third of the unicorns are from the e-commerce sector.

Sectors for Unicorn

Rank	Industry	No. of Unicorn	% of Total Values
1	E-Commerce	7	33%
2	Fin Tech	3	14%
3	Shared Economy	2	10%
4	Logistics	2	10%
5	On-Demand Delivery	2	10%
6	Renewable Energy	1	5%
7	Ed Tech	1	5%
8	Big Data	1	5%
9	Communication Platform	1	5%
10	Gaming	1	5%

Economics Survey 2022-23 by the Government of India, the e-commerce market is projected to grow at 18% annually through 2025. This e-commerce growth and rising focus on the government with initiatives such as ONDC and PM Gati Shakti National

Master Plan further strengthen the belief of business in the future of e-commerce in India and presents an opportunity to thousands of business across India.

Redseer report says that the Indian e-commerce industry is predicted to grow five fold to \$ 300 billion by 2030 with third party logistics providers expected to handle 17 billion shipments in the next seven years. It is 6-8 times of the 2022 level, as the third party logistics scales up, the cost per shipment is projected to decrease by 23% dropping from Rs 60 in 2023 to Rs. 47 by 2030.

E-commerce platforms have been highly successful in delivering standardized consumer experience on the platform while offering precisely the products in demand. The growth in direct to consumer brands to go digital and offer competitive shopping experiences. In all the efforts led to increased adoption and wallet share growth across customer cohorts while also driving robust and democratic sales across categories.

Over the last three years, new users who are willing to try e-commerce throughout the country have increased and non-metro users account for a large share of the total user base in FY 23. Indian e-tailing industry has gradually showed post-pandemic but continues to perform better than overall retail consumption to grow gross merchandise value (GVM) at 22% in FY 23 to reach 60 billion US\$ where the fourth quarter of 23 was effectively 2.5 times in scale compared to fourth quarter 20 (pre - Covid).

However the growth pattern in FY 23 is different where in the regular shoppers i.e. the monthly user base is now larger than ever before. The monthly shopper base which stood at 65 million US\$ in FY. 2023 is now 31% of the annual e-tailing shopper base - the same metric which was just 23% in a pre-pandemic era. This shows that the e-tailing user base is maturing and customers now shop online more frequently across a range of categories.

as a result of the category mix evolving towards non-mobile segments, the overall take rate of e-tailing industry has improved to 1.2 X from the pre-covid era. This allowed the industry's revenues to reach 6 billion \$ in FY. 23 and also set up the industry for robust revenue growth in future.

A strong environment sets to stage for ongoing e-commerce with Government e-market place saw a 160% growth, driven by 57% MSME Contribution. MSME revenue increased

by 194% through e-commerce adoption. During the pandemic 65% of MSEs upgrade their digital landscape, and 82% of Kirana stores adopted, new digital tools.

India leads with the world's highest mobile data consumption at 12GB per month. Users spend an average of 6 hours 37 minutes online daily. The average price for 1GB data is just US\$ 0.17, far below the global average of US\$ 3.12. Additionally users in India spend 156 minutes per day on smart phone entertainment content. With 800 million users, India was the second largest internet market in the world with 125.94 lakh crore UPI transaction in 2022.

A young demography, increasing internet and smart phone penetration and relatively better economic performance are some key drivers of this sector. Each month, India adds approximately 10 million daily internet users - the highest rate in the world, number of smart phones per 100 people has risen from 5.4 in 2014 to 26.2 in 2018.

India ranks third globally for startups; It has 16 e-commerce unicorns (Out of 109 World Wide) and attracted US\$ 15.4 billion in PE/VC investment in the e-commerce sector in 2022.

Redseer report - emphasizes the burgeoning adoption of e-commerce in Tier-2 and beyond cities. This combined with a growing base of mass consumers and the expansion of 3PL service ability, is catalyzing shipment volume. Consequently these volumes are projected to rise more sharply than GMV growth, The Redseer study Forecasts a 6 to 8 fold growth in 3 PL shipments from 2022 to 2030, rising from 2 billion in 2022 to a projected 13-17 billion in 2030. From January to August 2023, Meesho took the lead as the principal contributor to e-commerce 3PL shipments in India. Other major players included Flipcart, Ajo and Amazon, while vertical e-commerce platforms, D2C (direct-to-consumer) brands and smaller e-tailers accounted for the remaining shipments. 3PL has become essential for mass-focused horizontal, significant vertical and D2C brands. Partnering with 3PL for logistics need not only accelerates market entry but also drives growth and optimizing the challenges of erratic demand and optimizing logistics investment per shipment.

An analysis of Global Data's E-commerce analytics reveals that India's e-commerce market value is set to increase at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 28.2% from INR 2.8 trn (\$ 33.9 bn) in 2018 to INR 9.7 trn (\$117.3 bn) in 2023. This is driven by the rising internet and smartphone penetration, discounts, faster delivery option offered by online retailer and the growing consumer preference for online shopping.

The Indian Government also launched initiatives such as Startup India and Digital India, which also contributed to overall e-commerce growth. In addition, the Covid-19 pandemic too accelerated the shift to online shopping as wary consumers stayed home to avoid potential disease vectors.

This trend has persisted even after the reopening of physical stores. As a result e-commerce payment in India are forecast to grow at a CAGR of 22.4% between 2023 and 2027 to reach INR 21.8 trn in 2027.

According to Global Data's 2023 Financial Services Consumer Survey, alternative payment solutions dominate e-commerce in India with a combined market share of 58.1% in 2023. They have consistently gained popularity among the Indian consumers in the last five years with some of the popular brands being Amazon Pay, Google pay, and Paytm Payment cards are the second most popular e-commerce payment method in India with a share of 5.7% with credit and charge being preferred card types accounting for a 15.4% share in 2023. Cash which is widely used for in-store retail payment in India, has seen a significant drop in the market share for online purchases, accounting for only a 6.2% share.

E-Commerce Industry in India is primarily made of Consumer electronics and appeals segment together holding up to 80% of the overall market share. The major proportion of the e-commerce market in India is controlled by Flipkart with 16.10%. Followed by Amazon India with 5.05% of the overall market.

Conclusion

1. Rapid Growth - E-commerce in India has experienced rapid growth, driven by factors such as increasing internet penetration, smart phones usages and digital literacy.
2. Market Potential - Indian offers immense market potential due to its large population, rising middle class and increasing disposable income, making it an attractive destination for e-commerce business.
3. Diverse Consumer Base - India's diverse consumer base present both opportunities and challenges. Successful e-commerce ventures adopt their strategies to cater the diverse preferences, languages and culture nuances of Indian Consumer.
4. Mobile First Approach - With a significant portion of internet users accessing the web via smart phones, a mobile first approach is crucial for the success of e-commerce in India.
5. Logistics and Infrastructure - Efficient logistics and infrastructure are essential for timely delivery and customer satisfaction, especially in a geographically vast country like India.
6. Trust and Security - Building trust through secure payment gateways, transparent policies and excellent customer service is critical for the success and sustainability of e-commerce ventures in India.
7. Innovation and Adaptability - Successful e-commerce ventures in India continually innovate and adapt their strategies to stay ahead of the competition and meet the evolving needs of Indian consumer.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. Localization - Tailor the e-commerce platform to cater to the diverse languages, cultures and preference of Indian Consumers.
2. Mobile Optimization - Wide spread use of smart phones, ensure the platform is optimized for mobile devices to reach a larger audience.
3. Affordable Pricing - Offers competitive pricing and discounts to attract price - sensitive Indian consumers.

4. Logistics and Infrastructure - Invest in efficient logistics and infrastructure to ensure timely delivery, especially in remote areas.
5. Payment Options - Provide a variety of payment options, including cash on delivery, digital wallets, and UPI, to accommodate diverse preferences and accessibility.
6. Trust and Security - Establish trust through secure payment gateways, robust data protection measures, and transparent policies.
7. Customers Service - Offers excellent customer service in local languages to address queries and concerns promptly.
8. Market Place Model - Embraces the market place model to offer a wide range of products from various sellers, increasing choices for consumer.
9. Digital Literacy - Invest in initiatives to improve digital literacy among Indian consumer to increase adoption and usage of e-commerce platforms.
10. Personalization - Utilize data analytics to personalize recommendation and promotions based on consumer preferences and behavior.

References

1. Global Data Report - 2 October 2023.
2. Business Standard - 4 October 2023.
3. E-Commerce and Consumer Internet Sector - Indian Trend Book Mar.2021.
4. E-Commerce export conference Nov. 17, 2023 FICCI, New Delhi.
5. India Brand Equity Foundation Ministry of Commerce and Industry Report - Dec. 2023.
6. Press Information Bureau Government of India - Ministry of Commerce and Industry - 26/09/2019.
7. India Venture Capital Report - 2022.
8. Indian Trends Book - 2023.
9. Trade Promotion Council of India Report - October 2023.
10. Global Data's Financial Services Consumer Survey - 2023.
11. PE/VC Agenda - Indian Trend Book 2021.
12. Unlocking the potential of MSMEs in e-commerce, March 2022, NASSCOM Report.
13. <https://www.internationaltradecomplianceupdate.com/2019/03/22/india-releases-draft-national-e-commerce-policy/>,
14. <https://www.inspirajournals.com/uploads/Issues/448419972.pdf>
15. <https://business.outlookindia.com/news/national-e-commerce-policy-in-final-stages-to-be-presented-before-top-level-official-news-312201>
16. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaselframePage.aspx?PRID=1558567>,
17. <https://m.economictimes.com/small-biz/sme-sector/indias-e-commerce-market-to-be-worth-99-billion-by-2024-report/articleshow/81583312.cms>,
18. <https://www.tpci.in/indiabusiness/trade/blogs/india-the-next-powerhouse-of-global-e-commerce/>
19. <https://m.economictimes.com/industry/services/retail/e-commerce-to-grow-to-300-bn-by-2030-shipments-by-third-party-logistics-firms-to-17-billion-redseer-report/articleshow/104167749.cms>,
20. <https://retail.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/industry/d2c-brands-see-orders-surge-over-40-improved-their-prepaid-share-by-400-1000-basis-points-gokwik/100451662>,

21. <https://www.businesstoday.in/latest/corporate/story/indias-e-commerce-boom-gross-value-jumps-140-in-3-years-381979-2023-05-19>,

22. <https://www.tpci.in/indiabusinesstrade/blogs/india-the-next-powerhouse-of-global-e-commerce/>, 2030,

23. https://www.business-standard.com/industry/news/e-tailing-in-india-is-expected-to-grow-5x-to-300-bn-by-2030-redseer-123100400946_1.html,

24. https://www.business-standard.com/industry/news/e-tailing-in-india-is-expected-to-grow-5x-to-300-bn-by-2030-redseer-123100400946_1.html,

25. https://www.globaldata.com/newsletter/details/alternative-payments-account-for-nearly-60-of-e-commerce-market-in-india-reveals-globaldata_66188/?newsletterdate=2024-03-21